

Supplementary Information

High-resolution metabolomics reveals distinct pathways in septic patients that developed acute respiratory distress syndrome

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Supplementary Table 1. List of 316 discriminatory features in BAL

<i>mz</i>	time	VIP	Fold.change(ARDS/nonARDS)	Cluster
1111.2888	57.9	3.45	1.16	1
115.0869	41.2	2.86	1.25	1
399.2447	83.4	2.54	1.78	1
164.0293	108	2.48	1.83	1
1105.7724	57.3	2.43	1.13	1
208.0393	125.5	2.36	1.17	1
173.0672	115.8	2.32	1.31	1
171.0056	122.7	2.09	1.23	1
181.0143	218.8	2.02	1.27	1
226.012	276.2	2.01	1.78	1
143.5621	121.5	2.00	1.32	1
288.9217	119.3	1.87	1.31	1
154.0049	122	1.84	1.27	1
177.0246	121.5	1.78	1.52	1
180.0444	121.7	1.75	1.15	1
210.9355	136.5	1.75	1.49	1
398.2411	85.1	1.74	1.47	1
352.2328	564.1	1.72	1.14	1
104.0307	121.1	1.71	1.21	1
167.0128	125.7	1.70	1.13	1
337.1043	35.4	1.68	1.13	1
185.9419	126	1.61	1.53	1
97.9916	122.2	1.61	1.19	1
168.0161	125.6	1.60	1.21	1
354.2847	30.9	1.58	1.25	1
400.2476	82.8	1.58	1.80	1

198.0105	122.6	1.58	1.34	1
139.0179	122	1.56	1.23	1
156.9906	454.3	1.53	1.08	1
489.3394	55.6	1.51	1.08	1
552.6047	62.6	2.34	0.79	2
672.5594	62.9	2.23	0.79	2
682.5883	65.2	2.18	0.77	2
740.5466	63.2	2.12	0.85	2
674.5566	63	2.11	0.80	2
320.7703	62.5	2.11	0.83	2
318.7732	63.2	2.08	0.90	2
666.5247	62.7	2.04	0.73	2
732.5152	62.7	2.01	0.85	2
608.5662	62.7	1.85	0.85	2
664.5279	62.7	1.80	0.83	2
976.3744	62.6	1.75	0.84	2
778.4474	62.1	1.69	0.86	2
544.6164	62.4	1.69	0.83	2
730.5178	62.7	1.69	0.85	2
690.6198	63.8	1.63	0.84	2
786.435	62.1	1.63	0.86	2
744.541	65.1	1.62	0.85	2
862.4547	62.9	1.62	0.83	2
436.6875	62.8	1.62	0.88	2
918.416	62.7	1.56	0.86	2
678.5505	62.7	1.55	0.84	2
872.4831	63.2	1.55	0.84	2
798.5048	62.9	1.55	0.87	2
355.8055	63	1.55	0.86	2
742.5441	65.1	1.54	0.87	2
138.9064	65.6	1.52	0.96	2
604.5722	62.7	1.52	0.88	2
182.0329	119.8	3.33	1.27	3
114.5586	116.3	3.04	1.22	3
95.0443	116.3	2.91	1.24	3
103.0507	116.8	2.87	1.18	3
271.9646	115	2.82	2.98	3
153.0328	118.4	2.74	1.26	3
192.0617	118.2	2.73	1.29	3
194.0594	118.4	2.70	1.29	3

94.0455	119.9	2.70	1.21	3
123.0404	121.1	2.64	1.25	3
164.0668	116.7	2.62	1.20	3
115.5574	116.5	2.61	1.23	3
95.546	120.2	2.23	1.27	3
198.9651	123.8	2.20	1.30	3
1173.7598	57.3	2.13	1.10	3
193.0624	121.8	2.06	1.27	3
166.0644	120.3	1.98	1.21	3
470.8117	102.9	1.75	1.54	3
132.0032	65.7	1.71	1.05	3
107.0706	177.4	1.66	1.39	3
179.0539	117.4	1.65	1.12	3
125.038	121	1.63	1.18	3
184.0302	124.1	1.56	1.54	3
856.6369	62.4	2.59	0.72	4
733.5134	41.4	2.46	0.79	4
436.9025	62.7	2.25	0.81	4
620.8071	62.7	2.20	0.79	4
438.8995	62.7	2.04	0.88	4
213.0181	211.8	2.03	0.55	4
198.0512	113.5	1.98	0.75	4
320.9852	65	1.93	0.80	4
202.0598	121.9	1.92	0.68	4
123.0789	16.1	1.83	0.71	4
680.7627	62.7	1.78	0.81	4
430.9136	97.3	1.77	0.87	4
566.8415	63.2	1.76	0.79	4
670.7339	62.2	1.73	0.83	4
378.9438	70.8	1.70	0.79	4
740.7192	62.6	1.65	0.85	4
562.8485	62.9	1.65	0.83	4
564.8456	64.7	1.64	0.70	4
205.0681	176.9	1.62	0.82	4
381.9445	62.1	1.57	0.88	4
612.7755	62.4	1.55	0.85	4
206.0715	99.8	1.53	0.75	4
552.8198	62.4	1.53	0.82	4
635.8791	57.6	2.79	1.04	5
499.9044	58.1	2.56	1.04	5

237.1169	112.8	2.49	1.27	5
736.857	57.6	2.37	1.05	5
974.8129	57.5	2.23	1.06	5
1042.8003	57.8	2.15	1.03	5
237.1168	82.8	2.14	1.23	5
1110.7878	57.8	2.04	1.04	5
567.8918	57.6	1.96	1.05	5
906.8253	57.6	1.91	1.02	5
1043.3014	57.6	1.91	1.10	5
838.8378	57.9	1.88	1.03	5
770.8505	57.6	1.84	1.02	5
600.8822	57.6	1.76	1.04	5
96.9222	130.2	1.71	1.35	5
1178.7753	57.7	1.68	1.05	5
498.9009	57.7	1.67	1.03	5
702.8632	57.9	1.53	1.02	5
668.8697	57.5	1.50	1.03	5
194.0214	42.6	2.49	0.86	6
144.0807	68.1	2.13	0.45	6
154.9901	42.5	2.07	0.91	6
172.1524	144.4	2.06	0.69	6
131.0352	42.9	2.02	0.92	6
196.0167	42.4	1.97	0.86	6
152.9949	42.4	1.93	0.93	6
251.1849	449.6	1.84	0.90	6
498.8277	51.2	1.84	0.92	6
198.0849	121.5	1.76	0.78	6
119.0254	42.4	1.75	0.90	6
206.0208	43	1.70	0.88	6
211.9875	41.5	1.67	0.92	6
144.1383	72.8	1.66	0.55	6
157.0834	254.2	1.64	1.18	6
103.9555	19.3	1.62	0.64	6
170.985	43.5	1.59	0.89	6
304.894	53.3	1.56	0.95	6
191.0767	121.8	3.06	2.11	7
178.0086	123.3	2.57	1.67	7
199.9878	591	2.33	1.18	7
271.1453	148.6	2.19	1.33	7
197.1009	120.1	2.14	1.91	7

133.0972	125.3	2.02	1.58	7
297.2422	584.5	1.89	1.20	7
148.0604	116.9	1.79	1.52	7
453.2094	71.9	1.76	1.94	7
112.0872	117.8	1.71	1.37	7
107.0706	147.4	1.66	1.17	7
166.0862	88	1.66	1.63	7
372.0655	557.3	1.62	1.25	7
761.5876	17.3	1.62	1.65	7
374.0625	557.4	1.58	1.25	7
130.0863	120.7	1.56	1.44	7
98.5125	131.5	1.54	1.14	7
199.0293	270.7	1.54	1.09	7
313.2368	592.5	2.48	0.84	8
341.853	41.5	2.37	0.73	8
318.8208	137.2	2.12	0.74	8
309.8	135.7	2.09	0.80	8
140.0107	142	2.08	0.50	8
114.0916	280.1	1.88	0.93	8
227.9547	65	1.81	0.80	8
195.0199	42	1.75	0.73	8
109.0227	42.8	1.73	0.89	8
142.9481	139	1.72	0.58	8
569.3844	54.9	1.68	0.92	8
426.1126	557.4	1.66	0.90	8
164.93	138.3	1.65	0.64	8
362.926	97.1	1.61	0.85	8
115.0951	474.3	1.60	0.81	8
139.0178	280.4	1.55	0.82	8
129.1104	151.7	1.52	0.74	8
226.0119	121.9	1.51	0.85	8
178.0587	123.4	2.83	1.51	9
289.2929	84.2	2.51	2.79	9
150.0138	113.5	2.47	2.05	9
177.061	125.6	2.27	1.55	9
298.0525	126.3	2.26	1.92	9
449.353	39.1	2.14	1.13	9
192.0243	115.2	2.14	1.31	9
288.2893	82	1.99	1.74	9
303.8835	360.3	1.88	1.43	9

190.0497	555.1	1.88	1.28	9
316.3208	92.9	1.83	1.51	9
361.2322	556.1	1.81	1.17	9
975.3142	57.7	1.71	1.06	9
936.8043	57.1	1.63	1.08	9
179.143	555.8	1.61	1.14	9
120.0656	92.1	1.60	1.52	9
975.8157	57.8	1.60	1.06	9
1246.7628	57.9	2.50	1.09	10
1003.792	57.1	2.39	1.12	10
731.8426	57	2.09	1.11	10
453.1671	83.9	2.08	1.67	10
346.222	14.3	2.02	1.21	10
1212.7693	57.8	1.96	1.07	10
111.0205	389.2	1.82	1.10	10
500.9054	58.1	1.77	1.06	10
867.8172	57.1	1.75	1.04	10
429.2008	45	1.75	1.18	10
902.8098	57	1.74	1.08	10
940.8193	57.6	1.70	1.04	10
121.9746	130.6	1.69	1.25	10
1168.7448	56.6	1.64	1.10	10
873.3332	57.6	1.54	1.05	10
839.3395	57.6	1.53	1.05	10
217.926	104.9	2.30	0.75	11
325.0269	136.5	2.13	0.62	11
208.0393	433.6	2.10	0.65	11
120.0556	222.1	2.09	0.80	11
163.1328	477.5	2.08	0.94	11
222.0161	43.5	1.84	0.90	11
163.0008	71.2	1.74	0.83	11
225.9873	139.4	1.63	0.86	11
401.2872	125.1	1.61	0.52	11
340.2537	556.1	1.57	0.93	11
134.1176	128.5	1.55	0.80	11
251.185	370.4	1.54	0.86	11
537.316	55.2	1.54	0.88	11
532.4112	23.1	1.54	0.85	11
113.0601	383.9	1.53	0.80	11
111.0205	440.6	1.52	0.91	11

645.4611	41.6	2.52	0.84	12
213.9828	438	2.43	0.73	12
107.0706	570.7	2.22	0.75	12
448.3501	599.7	2.16	0.86	12
216.9226	182	1.86	0.65	12
196.0167	347	1.84	0.89	12
351.1403	77.6	1.84	0.58	12
180.0443	297.2	1.82	0.91	12
468.8148	102.9	1.73	0.69	12
151.0351	185.3	1.65	0.73	12
139.9878	299.9	1.62	0.71	12
354.2298	579.4	1.60	0.89	12
257.2666	41.4	1.55	0.80	12
295.2265	19.3	1.55	0.91	12
120.0556	231	1.55	0.75	12
130.0349	41.7	1.52	0.87	12
103.0506	211.6	2.80	1.16	13
1179.7772	57.8	2.69	1.15	13
414.2151	83.9	2.40	2.54	13
273.1362	108.5	2.34	2.35	13
222.8886	134.9	2.10	2.12	13
165.0691	117.7	2.09	1.71	13
251.1751	74.2	2.00	2.08	13
141.0064	124.7	1.91	1.44	13
158.986	196.3	1.81	1.40	13
242.9252	98.9	1.72	1.76	13
252.997	11.3	1.71	1.26	13
144.1019	114.9	1.66	1.80	13
144.0581	122.6	1.62	1.48	13
138.0273	121.7	1.62	1.18	13
271.2145	549.3	1.59	1.21	13
244.0414	128.4	2.38	0.74	14
288.9974	128.8	2.30	0.70	14
270.9641	121.8	2.09	0.67	14
154.0872	114.2	2.03	0.86	14
284.91	124.8	2.00	0.79	14
377.1454	127.1	1.97	0.81	14
144.9821	118.6	1.93	0.82	14
185.9903	132.1	1.76	0.56	14
243.0377	130.2	1.72	0.86	14

245.0335	130.2	1.71	0.87	14
377.1453	60.2	1.69	0.88	14
265.0193	130.6	1.67	0.83	14
197.0409	122.6	1.67	0.76	14
226.9513	65.6	1.56	0.88	14
335.1249	53.3	2.23	0.61	15
181.0284	126.1	2.10	0.56	15
777.5392	40.7	2.01	0.88	15
104.071	115.3	1.99	0.40	15
103.9555	38.7	1.96	0.80	15
324.9795	62.4	1.84	0.67	15
331.2476	484.9	1.71	0.84	15
227.9826	307.9	1.70	0.82	15
390.2848	28.4	1.65	0.78	15
512.3789	18	1.64	0.93	15
207.0723	62.1	1.63	0.85	15
344.2427	9.4	1.63	0.90	15
223.0964	555.3	1.59	0.84	15
362.8527	50.4	1.56	0.81	15
309.1306	545.9	2.43	0.84	16
119.0623	82.5	2.07	0.44	16
226.9514	96.5	2.02	0.89	16
137.0961	509.6	1.87	0.72	16
111.0205	565.3	1.80	0.94	16
120.0557	424	1.63	0.81	16
299.11	21.6	1.60	1.09	16
115.0951	544.3	1.57	0.91	16
186.9809	126.2	1.57	0.81	16
213.1596	270.9	1.50	0.92	16
250.9999	26.2	1.50	1.35	16
276.9815	120.6	2.84	0.67	17
124.9749	62.9	2.53	0.88	17
105.0426	97.3	2.14	0.53	17
610.5633	62.6	1.86	0.85	17
206.8938	177.9	1.81	0.85	17
936.4764	63.7	1.75	0.86	17
286.9067	65.2	1.66	0.92	17
256.0095	114.3	1.61	0.83	17
636.837	63.4	1.60	0.87	17
767.5068	62.4	1.59	0.86	17

233.8718	124.1	2.36	1.29	18
114.0664	69.1	1.88	1.98	18
193.9737	124.6	1.73	1.11	18
144.9821	55.7	1.71	1.07	18
237.117	124.7	1.70	1.26	18
132.0768	83.8	1.69	1.71	18
412.3604	126.3	1.63	1.60	18
167.9819	572.4	1.61	1.24	18
1071.7791	57.1	1.56	1.08	18
199.1803	165.4	1.54	1.19	18

Supplementary table 2. List of 369 discriminatory features in plasma

mz	time	VIP	Fold.change(ARDS/nonARDS)	Cluster
213.0182	149.2	2.43	1.20	1
288.9387	148.5	2.26	1.42	1
200.0076	148.4	2.23	1.20	1
97.9916	148.2	2.23	1.17	1
125.986	148.2	2.22	1.19	1
168.0161	148.4	2.19	1.16	1
156.9839	148.4	2.15	1.20	1
171.0056	148.6	2.08	1.21	1
208.0393	148.4	2.06	1.15	1
124.5436	147.9	2.04	1.19	1
167.0127	148.3	2.01	1.15	1
102.0342	147.4	2.01	1.15	1
104.0306	147.4	1.97	1.15	1
187.526	149.5	1.96	1.45	1
143.0604	148	1.93	1.14	1
131.5524	148.3	1.91	1.16	1
123.5505	148.1	1.91	1.16	1
304.6902	148.5	1.90	1.23	1
99.5316	148.2	1.90	1.16	1
210.0353	148.8	1.87	1.21	1
126.5422	148.2	1.87	1.24	1
139.0178	148.2	1.87	1.13	1
111.0394	147.6	1.87	1.15	1
111.541	148	1.86	1.15	1
157.0284	148.3	1.84	1.13	1
154.0049	148	1.80	1.13	1
199.0139	149.7	1.80	1.24	1
255.9439	148.8	1.73	1.38	1
90.5263	148	1.71	1.18	1
195.0315	148.1	1.66	1.12	1
296.9705	148.4	1.66	1.28	1
209.9475	149.1	1.62	1.19	1
122.5472	147.9	1.62	1.18	1
113.0359	148.4	1.62	1.19	1
193.9736	148.7	1.61	1.14	1
185.0233	148.7	1.55	1.14	1
223.1328	549.1	2.51	0.86	2

171.0957	149.5	2.45	0.46	2
328.248	562.5	2.38	0.82	2
281.2473	568.8	2.34	0.77	2
299.2578	569.9	2.25	0.77	2
300.2612	570	2.20	0.77	2
325.2371	563	2.20	0.73	2
317.2684	569.7	2.17	0.77	2
282.2506	569	2.17	0.78	2
318.2718	569.9	2.10	0.72	2
211.1692	569.2	2.03	0.79	2
355.2242	569.6	2.02	0.65	2
301.2643	570.2	1.99	0.74	2
255.1589	554.2	1.95	0.77	2
181.1586	569.3	1.94	0.76	2
264.24	569.3	1.81	0.75	2
245.2262	569.5	1.76	0.77	2
329.2514	562.6	1.76	0.79	2
332.3309	578.7	1.69	0.67	2
272.1854	554.1	1.69	0.79	2
339.2503	569.8	1.69	0.79	2
263.2367	569.1	1.69	0.83	2
340.2538	569.2	1.67	0.66	2
244.1905	522.2	1.66	0.66	2
369.2213	518.4	1.60	0.74	2
367.2243	518.2	1.59	0.82	2
256.1622	553.8	1.55	0.55	2
333.2633	504.9	1.53	0.85	2
247.0922	178.3	2.50	1.17	3
189.0869	178.3	2.41	1.16	3
235.0922	178.3	2.37	1.19	3
293.0975	178.2	2.32	1.16	3
294.1009	178.1	2.26	1.16	3
422.7461	123.6	2.21	1.56	3
638.0996	178.6	2.15	1.18	3
372.0712	178.9	2.15	1.27	3
585.1883	178	2.12	1.26	3
177.0869	178.3	1.98	1.17	3
260.9353	147	1.86	1.45	3
161.0636	178.3	1.86	1.14	3
316.0831	178	1.84	1.12	3

331.0534	178	1.80	1.15	3
332.0571	178	1.79	1.15	3
296.1051	197.7	1.78	1.46	3
317.0838	178	1.74	1.13	3
194.5255	179.7	1.71	1.14	3
315.0794	178	1.68	1.11	3
667.1076	165.3	1.67	1.22	3
111.5221	268.7	1.62	1.41	3
493.3132	84.3	1.60	1.16	3
639.1038	178.7	1.55	1.16	3
302.0195	180	1.55	1.07	3
424.7433	124.6	1.54	1.40	3
332.0052	570.5	2.42	0.81	4
198.1852	567.8	2.24	0.75	4
207.1743	504.1	2.24	0.89	4
348.9898	570.4	2.24	0.78	4
250.9999	570.5	2.22	0.83	4
252.997	570.5	2.18	0.80	4
350.9868	570.5	2.17	0.77	4
329.0049	570.4	2.16	0.84	4
225.196	558.6	2.14	0.84	4
277.2524	544.3	2.07	0.75	4
177.0246	139.8	2.06	0.61	4
330.0082	570.4	2.04	0.81	4
223.0635	549.4	2.02	0.81	4
328.0112	570.5	2.02	0.85	4
327.0078	570.5	1.96	0.74	4
332.9988	570.5	1.91	0.75	4
331.0019	570.4	1.90	0.75	4
414.0763	570.6	1.90	0.67	4
212.2008	478.7	1.86	0.68	4
133.0317	133.9	1.81	0.57	4
150.0583	109.9	1.71	0.60	4
174.9919	570.5	1.66	0.74	4
416.0732	570.5	1.64	0.71	4
147.1128	148.9	1.58	0.79	4
332.0052	551.8	2.91	1.35	5
183.0804	571.8	2.86	1.12	5
332.9988	551.8	2.81	1.34	5
329.0049	551.7	2.79	1.30	5

184.0837	571.8	2.78	1.11	5
328.0112	551.6	2.76	1.28	5
330.0082	551.8	2.75	1.28	5
327.0079	551.8	2.75	1.29	5
331.0019	551.8	2.74	1.27	5
252.997	551.8	2.73	1.29	5
250.9999	551.7	2.73	1.28	5
265.1044	543	2.72	1.77	5
98.9845	551.6	2.63	1.21	5
225.196	539.4	2.63	1.31	5
140.0107	551.7	2.37	1.19	5
309.1307	542.6	2.19	1.15	5
416.0733	551.8	2.12	1.76	5
151.1117	548.3	2.09	1.16	5
203.0066	157.4	2.03	1.51	5
130.5091	156.5	1.85	1.44	5
285.0941	570.4	1.77	1.22	5
414.0763	551.8	1.71	1.52	5
261.1095	519.7	1.69	1.05	5
235.1328	567.2	1.63	1.10	5
114.5586	144.2	2.46	1.19	6
163.1117	544.9	2.44	1.10	6
95.0442	143.8	2.34	1.18	6
115.5574	143.5	2.33	1.18	6
254.9866	144.8	2.31	1.41	6
194.0593	144.3	2.28	1.17	6
94.5441	144.4	2.27	1.22	6
164.0668	144.5	2.26	1.17	6
266.0164	144.8	2.25	1.71	6
125.038	144.2	2.17	1.16	6
256.9838	144.2	2.15	1.62	6
179.0539	144.1	2.14	1.15	6
169.0457	144.9	2.11	1.17	6
193.0623	145	2.04	1.14	6
265.0156	145.9	1.96	1.41	6
304.2843	135.9	1.91	1.33	6
124.0412	144.6	1.80	1.12	6
151.0352	178	1.71	1.64	6
199.521	199.3	1.71	1.23	6
153.0327	145.1	1.68	1.18	6

158.9612	382.2	1.61	1.23	6
165.0703	144.5	1.54	1.32	6
267.0129	144.9	1.54	1.33	6
354.0394	194.9	1.54	1.09	6
175.0313	160	2.54	1.41	7
674.0765	180	2.51	1.21	7
178.5505	160.5	2.47	1.34	7
187.041	159.7	2.38	1.31	7
295.102	163.1	2.34	1.17	7
186.5393	159.5	2.30	1.30	7
160.0603	162.9	2.25	1.17	7
182.5117	149.7	2.03	1.48	7
158.0372	160.6	1.92	1.26	7
317.9394	149.1	1.91	1.52	7
645.1263	164.3	1.89	1.20	7
246.5393	158.6	1.87	1.54	7
586.1918	163.8	1.86	1.37	7
332.048	160.7	1.83	1.23	7
377.0499	161.6	1.78	1.19	7
132.0655	163.4	1.78	1.20	7
198.0105	148.7	1.72	1.18	7
256.0574	159	1.70	1.46	7
188.5357	160	1.70	1.33	7
331.0445	159.8	1.62	1.17	7
276.9129	148.4	1.60	1.30	7
235.0923	200.4	1.54	1.25	7
623.1376	162.5	1.52	1.23	7
299.1099	526.8	2.57	0.87	8
344.2429	461.7	2.51	0.89	8
387.0401	570.3	2.40	0.79	8
352.9838	570.5	2.36	0.76	8
400.097	570.5	2.35	0.75	8
402.0941	570.5	2.27	0.74	8
214.2528	540.4	2.26	0.78	8
469.1111	570.7	2.20	0.72	8
389.0372	570.4	2.16	0.80	8
426.1127	570.5	2.13	0.76	8
230.2477	540.9	2.11	0.79	8
218.1539	542.2	2.06	0.84	8
467.1142	570.6	2.06	0.76	8

428.1097	570.5	2.01	0.79	8
331.2088	483.2	1.93	0.90	8
418.0703	570.3	1.80	0.79	8
309.1306	561.9	1.79	0.91	8
198.1489	475.2	1.65	0.77	8
261.1095	536.8	1.52	0.91	8
204.1383	509.3	3.12	1.22	9
223.1328	530.5	3.07	1.30	9
161.096	553.1	2.98	1.22	9
191.1641	515.2	2.91	1.32	9
311.1851	550.9	2.84	1.28	9
192.1382	528.8	2.73	1.15	9
277.128	511	2.66	1.24	9
223.0636	530.6	2.64	1.19	9
332.3309	132.4	2.54	1.90	9
279.0931	526.5	2.48	1.26	9
153.1273	550.8	2.21	1.23	9
286.958	515.8	2.15	1.99	9
326.3779	571.1	2.14	1.18	9
358.0208	193.4	2.01	1.08	9
373.2322	86.9	1.66	1.10	9
223.0635	578.4	1.66	1.30	9
89.0795	84.9	1.61	1.35	9
132.5313	241.6	1.56	2.09	9
160.0603	195.5	1.54	1.61	9
180.8943	225.2	2.31	0.37	10
158.0402	146.4	2.24	0.54	10
229.078	142.4	2.24	0.60	10
140.0682	147.5	2.15	0.66	10
362.926	124.1	2.12	0.49	10
156.0421	146.8	1.99	0.58	10
269.1356	505.9	1.97	0.82	10
208.1776	504.1	1.93	0.84	10
88.0761	67.9	1.93	0.79	10
213.1458	531.5	1.84	0.90	10
198.0172	483.2	1.74	0.78	10
171.9929	428.2	1.69	0.72	10
645.4612	69.1	1.66	0.92	10
244.0317	155.2	1.62	0.63	10
113.9637	438.4	1.61	0.82	10

99.0445	486.8	1.61	0.72	10
337.0614	191.8	1.58	0.81	10
429.2007	67.1	1.51	0.84	10
178.9906	231.2	2.33	1.35	11
110.0086	145.1	2.22	1.47	11
362.8526	79.8	2.07	1.16	11
157.0834	248.2	2.06	2.02	11
141.0063	146.1	1.97	1.26	11
369.0095	194.7	1.85	1.19	11
280.9929	146.8	1.83	1.23	11
151.0352	564.4	1.82	1.48	11
190.0902	164	1.78	1.30	11
149.0597	133.3	1.73	1.84	11
740.5222	22	1.72	1.80	11
112.8959	102.6	1.68	1.11	11
229.1408	87.5	1.64	1.19	11
236.0957	161.8	1.63	1.49	11
532.8948	88.1	1.63	1.16	11
148.0604	146.8	1.61	1.51	11
159.024	146.9	1.59	1.16	11
270.9641	147.3	1.58	1.24	11
249.0608	107.9	2.25	0.39	12
137.0727	129.9	2.15	0.62	12
249.1068	97.5	2.13	0.39	12
172.0385	143.7	2.07	0.67	12
217.0164	148.5	2.06	0.68	12
184.0653	150.7	2.02	0.66	12
760.5832	67.5	1.98	0.76	12
191.0402	140	1.97	0.80	12
170.985	68.7	1.77	0.80	12
207.0141	140.1	1.72	0.81	12
169.0582	142.4	1.70	0.67	12
113.0512	143.2	1.69	0.61	12
189.0738	108.2	1.67	0.64	12
341.2294	88.8	1.63	0.90	12
171.0763	145	1.59	0.80	12
188.0705	108.2	1.57	0.65	12
354.8942	116.3	1.57	0.89	12
249.1079	159.5	1.54	0.73	12
265.1044	562	2.79	0.72	13

210.1852	545.9	2.77	0.78	13
311.1851	569.6	2.69	0.79	13
310.2375	534.9	2.63	0.71	13
284.961	532.3	2.62	0.75	13
172.1695	531.1	2.56	0.86	13
286.958	532.3	2.56	0.76	13
353.2221	479.6	2.53	0.61	13
270.2062	529.3	2.51	0.70	13
158.1539	558.4	2.46	0.77	13
161.096	571.6	2.34	0.89	13
266.2112	542.2	2.30	0.77	13
182.1539	494.3	2.23	0.85	13
159.1572	558.4	2.06	0.71	13
411.2063	569.2	1.88	0.66	13
277.128	527	1.83	0.90	13
207.1743	550.5	2.32	1.11	14
207.159	472.3	2.25	1.32	14
380.2558	530.1	2.05	1.30	14
346.0093	510	2.00	1.64	14
370.8683	120	1.95	1.41	14
123.5452	148.2	1.92	1.40	14
308.8262	125.5	1.92	1.64	14
165.1274	549.8	1.92	1.22	14
223.9882	158	1.87	1.34	14
217.0818	151.7	1.81	2.13	14
263.0873	178	1.80	1.39	14
134.0448	178	1.72	1.52	14
309.2269	469.1	1.64	1.13	14
436.8587	118.9	1.62	1.65	14
223.0964	524.9	1.59	1.12	14
128.107	173.4	1.52	1.44	14
355.2242	550.9	2.93	2.58	15
332.3309	561.5	2.76	1.99	15
333.2633	490.6	2.68	1.73	15
193.1587	550.6	2.39	1.29	15
239.1277	519.9	2.26	1.10	15
225.1484	539.9	2.26	1.14	15
315.2528	535	2.25	1.37	15
295.2265	29.3	2.03	1.20	15
297.2422	534.4	1.98	1.25	15

264.2401	550.3	1.84	1.53	15
198.1488	489.3	1.79	1.65	15
228.1957	531.2	1.73	1.12	15
279.2317	534.6	1.72	1.12	15
315.2083	576.6	1.57	1.30	15
826.5204	84.8	1.52	1.21	15
158.0679	134.2	2.29	0.70	16
404.1027	543.8	2.11	0.76	16
199.1009	108.1	2.07	0.75	16
143.0396	360	2.03	0.68	16
267.1103	140.6	1.89	0.54	16
203.1502	145.9	1.86	0.75	16
192.0617	551.8	1.77	0.66	16
251.1364	140.5	1.74	0.47	16
781.5546	154.7	1.74	0.71	16
237.1168	112.1	1.57	0.90	16
238.1201	112.1	1.55	0.90	16
310.2373	21.2	1.54	0.88	16
241.1545	138.1	1.52	0.65	16
172.0401	103.9	1.51	0.65	16
304.2997	560.8	2.28	0.72	17
239.1752	530.8	2.02	0.82	17
352.8972	115.9	1.71	0.87	17
189.1637	568.8	1.67	0.75	17
223.0964	568.8	1.66	0.92	17
182.9851	542.7	1.61	0.73	17
371.0194	181	1.59	0.74	17
309.2269	483	1.55	0.89	17
322.2738	569.1	1.52	0.82	17
197.1535	568.8	1.52	0.87	17
163.1117	526.8	1.51	0.92	17
298.3466	570.6	1.51	0.80	17
331.2088	469.2	2.43	1.29	18
123.0489	459.9	2.21	1.42	18
182.1539	479.9	2.06	1.27	18
344.243	444.9	1.99	1.34	18
328.7559	99.1	1.72	1.16	18
198.1852	533.8	1.69	1.14	18
94.0455	265.8	1.56	1.22	18
197.0205	64.2	1.52	1.30	18

255.1589	535.2	1.51	1.32	18
279.2316	575.1	1.50	1.23	18
154.8803	134.7	1.88	0.67	19
310.201	104.9	1.85	0.59	19
430.2852	87.3	1.82	0.94	19
150.9323	135.3	1.72	0.72	19
273.1208	148.1	1.70	0.62	19
212.8389	134.3	1.64	0.52	19
129.1022	85.8	1.62	0.73	19
286.201	122.3	1.58	0.65	19
160.9681	90.8	1.55	0.86	19
186.9808	68.4	1.51	0.60	19

Supplementary Figure 1. Boxplots of BAL discriminatory features associated with ARDS ($p < 0.05$) status after adjusting for potential confounding variables (source of infection and diabetes status)

Supplementary Figure 2. Boxplots of plasma discriminatory features associated with ARDS ($p < 0.05$) status after adjusting for potential confounding variables (source of infection and diabetes status)

